

MACHINE TRANSLATION TOOLS IN TRANSLATION PROCESS

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Annotation: This article provides a comprehensive overview of Machine Translation (MT) tools and their integration into the translation process. It traces the development of MT systems from early rule-based methods to modern neural machine translation (NMT), highlighting the technological advancements that have made tools like Google Translate and DeepL widely accessible. The article addresses the benefits of MT, including its speed and cost-effectiveness, as well as its limitations, particularly in terms of translation quality and cultural context. The article emphasizes the ongoing role of human translators, especially in tasks requiring post-editing of machine-generated translations, and discusses the future prospects of MT tools in professional settings. By offering a balanced view of MT's current capabilities and challenges, the article provides valuable insights into the evolving landscape of translation technologies.

Keywords: Translation tools, machine translation, automation, computers systems.

Machine Translation (MT) has become an essential component of the translation process, transforming both professional practices and everyday communication across linguistic boundaries. MT refers to the use of computer-based systems that automatically translate text from one language to another. Over the years, advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and computational linguistics have driven significant improvements in the accuracy and fluency of MT systems, leading to widespread adoption across industries. Initially, rule-based systems dominated the MT landscape, relying on predefined linguistic rules to translate text. According to Bahdanau and Koehn, the advent of statistical machine translation (SMT) in the 1990s, followed by neural machine translation (NMT) in the 2010s, brought remarkable improvements in translation quality.

Today, MT tools such as Google Translate, DeepL, and Microsoft Translator are ubiquitous, offering rapid and cost-effective translation solutions for a variety of purposes, from casual communication to professional document translation. Wu defined that these systems process vast amounts of bilingual data to generate translations that are increasingly accurate and contextually appropriate. When it comes Torres-Hostench, however, he said that while MT offers significant

benefits in terms of speed and accessibility, human translators are still needed for tasks requiring high levels of precision, nuance, and cultural adaptation. While Garcia gives another view, consequently, the translation process often involves a hybrid approach, with human translators performing post-editing to refine machine-generated output. Despite the significant advantages MT offers, such as speed and accessibility, the role of human translators remains crucial, particularly for texts that require high levels of nuance, creativity, or cultural adaptation. As MT tools continue to evolve, the interaction between human expertise and machine-generated translations is increasingly seen as a collaborative process, often referred to as post-editing. This process allows human translators to refine and adjust machine-generated output to ensure accuracy and appropriateness in the target language.

In this article, we explore the role of MT tools in the translation process, examining their capabilities, limitations, and the ways they are reshaping the translation industry. We also discuss the implications of ongoing technological advancements and the future of human-MT collaboration in translation.

A machine translation tool is a software application that automates the process of converting source language text into target language text. The level of human intervention required for this translation is minimal, often limited to a few clicks, as the majority of the process is pre-programmed and automated.

The direct translation approach involves the machine program, or MT tool, recognizing the target language input, matching it with entries in a dictionary, and generating the corresponding target language output. In contrast, the transfer approach involves analyzing words, phrases, sentences, and paragraphs in the source language, identifying their equivalents in the "database" of the machine, and generating the target language output based on these equivalents.

Now let's look the translation tools with their general functions:

Google Translate, a free multilingual machine translation service developed by Google, allows users to input text in their native language and receive the translated output in the desired language. This tool not only provides a convenient way to communicate across language barriers but also offers a dictionary-like approach to language learning, providing meanings of terms, translation information, and example phrases or sentences.

With Google Translate, users can translate large volumes of text or entire web pages, copy, share, listen to, and save the translated text. The service even enables users to produce simple translations that are sufficient for readers unfamiliar with the target language to understand the meaning. When Google

Translate generates a translation, it analyzes hundreds of millions of documents to identify patterns that can help it select the most appropriate translation for the user.

The role of a translator extends beyond merely providing word definitions and synonyms. In the realm of online translation tools, there exists a platform that caters to over 60 different languages, empowering users to effortlessly input words, phrases, or even entire sentences, enabling them to receive instant translations.

While this online translator may not offer the same level of features as standalone translators, it remains a valuable tool for swift translations. What sets it apart is its simplicity, allowing users to easily copy the translated text. Furthermore, Bing Microsoft Translator is a cloud-based multilingual translation service, capable of translating text from one language to another, as well as converting text into speech, as demonstrated by Dorman et al.

The users may articulate a word, phrase, or sentence they wish to translate, and hear the translation aloud. They can also copy, share, or utilize Bing to search the web if their microphone is activated.

In contrast to Google Translate, which supports more than 100 languages, Microsoft's Bing Translator supports over 60 languages and up to 5,000 characters. Additionally, it introduces a feature allowing users to provide some input regarding the translation process.

Yandex Translator, on the other hand, does not limit itself to standard text translations but goes beyond to translate images and websites in 99 different languages, making it the premier online translator for diverse purposes. Its user-friendly interface, rapid operation, and potential for language learning make it an invaluable tool. Users can switch between languages while interpreting an image without the need to re-upload it, provided they have already uploaded it for translation. Furthermore, it incorporates predictive text input, a dictionary with transcription, audio pronunciation, examples of how to utilize the word or phrase, and corrections for inaccurate translations.

The service known as Translate is capable of translating brief documents up to 3,000 characters in length for free. Any website or web page can be translated into any desired language, providing options for fluid navigation, alternative meanings, presentation, and more.

The service receives text and file translations on-the-fly via email. It is a free web-based language translation service that offers a convenient self-service option for swiftly translating the information we need.

IBM Translator (IT), on the other hand, provides instant translation of documents, applications, and websites, allowing us to expand into new markets. This software converts documents between languages while preserving their layout, type, and all supported file formats. Neural machine translation is employed by default for all language pairs, leveraging deep learning to enhance translation speed and accuracy.

Machine translation tools have had a significant impact on the translation process, presenting both opportunities and challenges for professional translators and the wider field of translation studies. With technological advancements continuing to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of machine translation (MT), these tools have become an indispensable resource for many translators, allowing them to manage larger volumes of text more quickly.

While MT tools do offer speed and consistency, their ability to capture the nuances of language, cultural context, and idiomatic expressions remains limited, highlighting the importance of human expertise in these areas. Despite this, MT tools continue to play a valuable role in the translation process by reducing costs and increasing efficiency, making them an essential tool for translators seeking to meet deadlines and deliver high-quality translations.

Despite these limitations, the incorporation of machine translation (MT) into the translation process should be seen as an addition to, rather than a replacement for, human translation. The combination of MT and human post-editing has proven to be an effective strategy, enabling translators to make the most of both machine capabilities and human creativity. Moreover, the ongoing advancement of neural machine translation and artificial intelligence offers hope for overcoming some of the current challenges associated with MT, making it an important tool in the ever-changing landscape of global communication.

In summary, machine translation (MT) tools are revolutionizing the translation industry by speeding up, enhancing efficiency, and facilitating the process. Nevertheless, it is important to recognize that MT should be viewed as a complementary tool in a hybrid model that combines human expertise with technological innovation to ensure accurate and culturally appropriate translations. As technology continues to advance, the interaction between MT and human translators will likely continue to develop, offering increasingly sophisticated solutions for the challenges of multilingual communication.

Reference:

1. Bahdanau, D., Cho, K., & Bengio, Y. (2014). Neural Machine Translation by Jointly Learning to Align and Translate. arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.0473.

2. García, I. (2015). Post-editing of Machine Translation: A Survey. *MonTI: Monografías de Traducción e Interpretación*, 7, 13-28.
3. Koehn, P. (2009). *Statistical Machine Translation*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Torres-Hostench, O. (2018). The Role of the Human Translator in the Age of Machine Translation. *Translation Journal*, 22(3), 15-24.
5. Wu, Y., Schuster, M., Chen, Z., Le, Q. V., Norouzi, M., Macherey, W., & Krikun, M. (2016). Google's Neural Machine Translation System: Bridging the Gap between Human and Machine Translation. arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.08144.